

README

Localization of Historical House Sites in Austria

Methodological Approach and Exemplary Case Studies

This publication addresses the general research question and methodology of locating historical house and farmstead sites based on individual historical mentions. The methodological application is demonstrated through the case of Annabichl No. 4, vulgo Michitz, in Klagenfurt - Annabichl (Carinthia, Austria).

Content

The publication consists of the following components:

localization_publication_german.pdf

Main document presenting the methodological approach and case study in German.

localization_publication_english.pdf

Main document presenting the methodological approach and case study in English.

michitz_annabichl_datasheet01_german.pdf

Data sheet with detailed documentation of sources and localization in German.

michitz_annabichl_datasheet01_english.pdf

Data sheet with detailed documentation of sources and localization in English.

Documentation

The main document contains:

- Description of the research question
- Explanation of the methodological approach
- Discussion of methodological limitations
- Detailed elaboration of the case study
- Summary of the results

The accompanying data sheet contains:

- Structured documentation of the sources used
- Spatial assignment of the historical mentions
- Georeferenced location data
- Additional contextual information on the case

Methodological note

Localization is achieved through the comparison of multiple independent characteristics derived from historical and spatial sources. A localization is only considered reliable if several independent criteria correspond.

No identity between historical and present-day buildings is assumed. In particular, address continuity should not be equated with structural continuity.

Temporal and spatial changes, especially re-parcellation and infrastructural transformations, must be taken into account in the interpretation.

License

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0)

This publication and the accompanying data sheet may be used and redistributed, provided that the author is properly credited.

Author

Brigitta Szekely

Austria

ORCID: 0009-0006-0538-0737

Recommended citation

Szekely, Brigitta (2026):

Localization of Historical House Sites in Austria: Methodological Approach and Exemplary Case Studies (Version 1.0).

Zenodo. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19385406>

Contact

szekely dot research [at] gmail dot com